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THE IMPORTANCE OF PRACTICAL FACTORS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF NATIONAL SELF-CONSCIOUSNESS AND THE IDEOLOGY OF NATIONAL INDEPENDENCE

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ABSTRACT

The article highlights the factors that contribute to the introduction of national identity and the ideology of national independence, reveals the importance of historical series, the media, education and upbringing, publishing products in this process.

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Historical experience shows that during the transition of society from one formation to another, a person may experience an ideological void in a certain sense. Based on this, in order to prevent an ideological vacuum in the minds of young people in our country, the concept of national independence has been developed. An important place in the upbringing of a harmoniously developed young generation is occupied by the focus of young people on a careful respectful attitude to the rich spiritual heritage of their ancestors, to the national values of our people. Therefore, the main postulate of the ideology of national independence is the construction of a free and prosperous state, a free and prosperous life”. In modern conditions of globalization of society, the idea and ideology of national independence can be introduced into the minds of people not only through the education system and not through lengthy reports and lectures, but mainly through a system of practical actions. The

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan emphasized that in the modern world there are things directed against the spirituality of a person. It would seem that a completely insignificant message can excite the entire information world, at first glance, an imperceptible, but frankly harmful thought can cause great harm.

“We all know very well that to keep state borders inviolable, military power and armed forces are necessary, like water and air, but our people strive, first of all, to educate the younger generation in an atmosphere of spiritual security and think about how what values we should rely on. This is our common duty ". In this context, one of the factors influencing the minds of young people, which was mentioned above, are serials on historical topics. In recent years, TV series of Korean , Chinese masters of cinema, dedicated to historical figures and events, for example, the historical series “Genghis Khan” created by Chinese filmmakers. It should be noted here that we are talking not so much about cinema and the level of skill, but about national self-consciousness and the degree to which the ideology of national independence is introduced into the mass consciousness. If we talk about great historical figures and historical events, then we need to mark. It can be said that our famous ancestors are among the great people who stood at the cradle of the spiritual world.

Our filmmakers studied a lot of historical and archival materials and created a new version of the series about Amir Temur and Bibikhanum, which deserved positive feedback from viewers. Or a film about the great scientist-encyclopedist Ibn Sino, who made an invaluable contribution to the development of world medicine, a series about a fighter for national independence and liberation from the Mongol yoke Jaloliddin Manguberdi. Such series undoubtedly help viewers appreciate the role of great compatriots. In order for a historical series to be reliable and well received, certain conditions are needed for its creation. Among them: the economic base for the historical series; correspondence of the theme of the series to the spirit of the time; completeness, completeness of the script; scenario level; selection of expressive means; selection of visual means, artistic power and value; acting skills, a departure from pretense, a sense of responsibility; performance technique; perfection of interpretation of images; correlation of speech and image; rational use of cinema and television genres; Continuity in matters of the historical past - today's realities - the future. We all are well aware of the strong and rapid impact that cinema as a form of aesthetic art has on the consciousness and spiritual world of a person.

The publishing system also makes an invaluable contribution to the formation of national self-consciousness, primarily through the printing of color photographs of great ancestors, the release of color photo albums depicting world-famous architectural monuments and sights of cities and the modern life of the republic. Such printed materials, accompanied by comments in two or three foreign languages, certainly attract the attention of foreign guests and arouse their great interest in our republic, and, consequently, the possibilities for promoting the ideology of national independence are expanding. With the transition of our country to market economic relations, it became necessary to overcome the old thinking among a significant part of the population, and this process is associated with patient work to explain the advantages of a new type of social and economic relations, the policy of evolutionary transformation, and careful attitude to people's feelings. National self-awareness is not only awareness, the introduction of the ideology of national independence is not just implementation, they must be considered as an interconnected process of awareness and implementation.

The Renaissance in Central Asia resulted in the greatest achievements in the political, economic

and spiritual life of society. During this period, political and legal sciences, new literature and art, medicine, philosophy, and a new aesthetic consciousness were created.¹

As of now, the state policy of women, including women, in Uzbekistan, to protect the legitimate and social interests of women, to ensure full participation of women in the political life of the country, to ensure gender equality and reproductive health, is highly appreciated by the world community, namely, the International Labour Organization, UNICEF, the World Health Organization.²

The revival of national values should be perceived in the context of their harmonization with modern universal values. The revival of national-spiritual values, their deep assimilation, explanation on the basis of ideological tasks becomes a spiritual necessity. The head of our state emphasizes that the development of national self-consciousness is carried out very quickly. In general, this is a positive process, but at the same time, there are also negative phenomena on the path of development. Therefore, the first task is to identify the reasons that impede the growth of national self-consciousness and outline ways that positively affect this process.

The article examines the most important issues of the formation of the rule of law and civil society in modern Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan has a rich experience of political life, features of political consciousness and develops in unique and difficult conditions. Thus, it turned out that it is wrong to copy a simple copy of the political experience of the Western world.³

The paper investigates the essence of spiritual potential as well as its role in modern society.⁴

An important task in solving the problem of the development of national self-consciousness is to counter the influence of the former Soviet system. And this requires a deep knowledge and understanding of the values of acquired independence. It is especially important to convey to the minds of young people the essence of the ideas of independence, to show what changes have taken place in the minds of people who at one time experienced a state of complete enslavement and submission. But this is only one side of the issue. No less important is the increase in the level of educational and practical work with young people, the wide dissemination of experience in working with the youth of developed countries, the formation of love for their profession, humane principles, a sense of responsibility for the fate of the Motherland and the people in the young generation, which contributes to a strong awareness of belonging to their own country. nation, people.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.
2. Фуломжонов, О. Р. Ў. (2021). ЖАМИЯТ ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ ЯНГИ БОСҚИЧИДА ГЕНДЕР ТЕНГЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Scientific progress*, 1(4).
3. Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2021). STRUCTURE, MODELS AND CHARACTERISTICS OF CIVIL SOCIETY. *STRUCTURE*, 7(4).
4. Talantbek, M., & Omonillo, E. (2022). SPIRITUAL POTENTIAL AND ITS ROLE IN MODERN. " *Yosh Tadqiqotchi*" *jurnali*, 1(2), 58-62.

¹ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

² Фуломжонов, О. Р. Ў. (2021). ЖАМИЯТ ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ ЯНГИ БОСҚИЧИДА ГЕНДЕР ТЕНГЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Scientific progress*, 1(4).

³ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2021). STRUCTURE, MODELS AND CHARACTERISTICS OF CIVIL SOCIETY. *STRUCTURE*, 7(4).

⁴ Talantbek, M., & Omonillo, E. (2022). SPIRITUAL POTENTIAL AND ITS ROLE IN MODERN. " *Yosh Tadqiqotchi*" *jurnali*, 1(2), 58-62.